

Linear Free-Energy Relationship in Mixed Solvents

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The nature of the variations of ρ with solvent systems has been explored. The change in ρ -values cannot be explained on the basis of electrostatic theory. The changes in ρ - and σ -values have been tried to be correlated with changes in field and mesomeric effects.

THE role of solvents on the dissociation constants of weak acids has not been well-understood. It has been well established that solute-solvent interactions of uncertain magnitude have a profound effect on the dissociation constants which could not be well explained on the basis of simple electrostatic theory.

Little attempt, however, has been made to elucidate the role of solvents on the Hammett's reaction parameter ρ . The ρ -value is dependant on the reaction, nature of the solvent system and temperature^{1,2}. Thus, the change of the solvent should have a profound effect on ρ .

In order to elucidate the effect of solvents on ρ , we determined the dissociation constants of benzoic acid, *m*-chloro, *m*-fluoro, *p*-bromo and *p*-iodo benzoic acids in ethanol-water and methanol-water mixtures by the modified conductometric method suggested by Gelb³ and also by Fuoss-Kraus method⁴. Since σ -values are generally assumed to be independent of solvent, the pK -values of benzoic acids in methanol+water and ethanol+water mixtures should be a linear function of the corresponding pK -values of benzoic acids in water.

The Hammett equation in water (W) and other solvents (S) can be represented as :

$$pK_A(W) = pK_{A_0}(W) - \rho_w \sigma \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{and } pK_A(S) = pK_{A_0}(S) - \rho_s \sigma \quad \dots (2)$$

A = Substituted acid,
A₀ = Unsubstituted acid.

Thus, we have,

$$pK_A(S) = (\rho_s/\rho_w) pK_A(W) + [pK_{A_0}(S) - (\rho_s/\rho_w)pK_{A_0}(W)] \quad \dots (3)$$

for the relationship $pK_A(S)$ and $pK_A(W)$. Thus, from the plots of $pK_A(S)$ against $pK_A(W)$ should give straight lines⁵ from the slope of which ρ_s/ρ_w , thus ρ_s could be calculated since $\rho_w = 1$. This can also be obtained from the relationship (2).

With the limited data available, we are able to find ρ_s -values in different mixed solvents. The ρ_s -values show maximum in the region 60-80 wt% of organic solvents (Table 1) similar to the observations of Rochester⁶ and others⁶.

TABLE-1

Wt % of MeOH	8.0	16.0	25.0	34.4	44.7	54.2	64.1	75.9
	1.01	0.92	0.99	1.10	1.16	1.27	1.55	1.25
Wt % of EtOH	8.0	16.4	25.3	34.4	44.0	54.1	64.7	76.0
	0.80	0.73	0.90	0.94	1.10	1.18	1.33	1.11

ρ -values have been observed to be consistently more positive in methanol-water than in ethanol-water mixtures. At low percentages of the organic solvents ρ is less than 1 and becomes more than 1 near about 0.1 mole-fraction of organic solvent. This can probably be correlated with the significant structural and consequent entropy changes in the medium around 0.1 mole-fraction of alcohol⁷. It is known that an enhancement of solvent structure occurs and becomes maximum around $X_2 = 0.1$ of alcohol⁸. The increasing positive value of ρ in mixed solvents indicates the greater facilities for the development of partial negative charge on the side-chain⁹ which is more pronounced in methanol-water than the corresponding ethanol-water mixtures. This must be related to medium effects as everything is common except the solvent systems.

For the reaction :

We have,

$$pK = \rho \sigma = \frac{\Delta G_{\text{noneq}}}{2.303 RT} + \frac{\Delta G_{\text{el}}}{2.303 RT} = \frac{\Delta G_{\text{noneq}}}{2.303 RT} + \frac{Ne^2}{2 \times 2.303 RT \epsilon} \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_{A_0^-}} - \frac{1}{\gamma_{A^-}} \right) \quad \dots (5)$$

Thus, a linear relationship of ρ against $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$ is expected. But the relationship fails in mixed solvents. This

is quite natural due to the approximate nature of the Born equation¹⁰ where the dielectric constant have been regarded to be the macroscopic dielectric constant. Polarization of the solvent molecules by ions and consequent changes of the dielectric constant have been neglected altogether. No theoretical equation, however, exists to account for the variations of the dielectric constant with radii of ions though the dielectric constant is known to be a function of radii of ions¹¹. The equations^{12,13} which account for the variations in dielectric constant with distance are purely empirical and inadequate. Even the theory of Hiromi¹⁴ which takes into account the particular geometry and charge distribution with organic ion is inadequate as the equation also predicts the variation of pK with $1/\epsilon$. It is, however, known that the dielectric constant is not the only property which determines the variations in pK but medium effects, i.e., solute-solvent interactions, solvent-basicity and solvent-structure, etc., are of importance to know the nature of the variations of ρ with solvent systems.

The failure of the relationship may be partly due to changed values of σ in mixed solvents due to change in medium effects. σ is known to change with solvent as evident from the works of Bright and Briscoe¹⁵ and others^{2,16}. This is also apparent from theoretical point of view as explained by Dewar and Grisdale¹⁷:

σ is dependant on (1) direct electrostatic (or field) effect and (2) mesomeric effect, i.e.,

$$\sigma^- = F/\gamma_{ij} - M\pi_{ij} \quad \dots (6)$$

F and M are constants determining the field and resonance effect, π_{ij} and γ_{ij} are the atom-atom polarizability of the aromatic system and the distance between the points of attachment to the aromatic system of the substituent and side-chain respectively.

In spite of the limitations of the equations, it has been successfully utilised by Dewar and Grisdale¹⁷.

No theoretical treatment of evaluation of ρ -values has been made. It is reasonable to believe that the field and mesomeric effects and the complex interactions the reactants undergo in solution should be responsible for the change in ρ -values.

The direct electrostatic effect is dependant, besides other factors, on the effective dielectric constant¹⁸ which definitely changes with change in the solvent systems leading to a change in the σ -values, mesomeric effect probably will have little

effect in changing σ -values in mixed solvent. However, it is not definite as to what extent the dielectric constant affects the σ -values.

A correlation of ρ -values calculated from pK values of well-behaved meta-substituted compounds with γ -values has been made by Grunwald et al¹⁹, σ -values are regarded to be independent of solvents in his treatment also.

It is thus apparent that unambiguous method for the evaluation of ρ - and σ -values in mixed solvents as well as more data are needed before any correlation of ρ -values with γ - or any other solvent parameter could be made.

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